

Appendix 1: Nominal group meeting guide.

Introduction, process explanation, and preliminary information.

- **Thank participants for participating and explain the purpose of the Study.**
- **Introduce self.**
- **Explain Nominal group meeting process.**

During this meeting, we will present you with the results of the survey. However, our objective is to review a selection of the recommendations on which you all reached a consensus, some of the recommendations where the recommendations were applicable, recommendations where you all agreed that the recommendations were not relevant, and two or three recommendations where you just could not reach a consensus. The purpose of this meeting is to get insight into the reasoning behind your assignment of a consensus score to each recommendation.

I am going to lead the interview (SF). We would like to record this to give us some data to, as I said, sort of understand how people go about adapting national clinical guidelines. So my colleague (SA) will have circulated an information sheet and a consent form. All of the usual caveats apply, so nobody will know that you have participated in this interview. We will report quotations from the interview meeting, but we will not attribute them to any specific individual within this group. We will store the data in a secure location and destroy it after the study is complete. Please feel free to answer or ask any questions about what we need to do today.

Part 1 questions:

A couple of the recommendations for incorporation lacked consensus. Consensus refers to the requirement that the recommendation's median score be seven or greater. The first group of chosen recommendations did not reach a consensus on their inclusion in the guidelines for managing gait disorders after a stroke. Considering the significant differences among all of you as a group, I believe it would be advantageous to begin at this point and discuss each specific recommendation for every individual. We have several questions about these particular recommendations that we'd like to ask you. Kindly provide an indication of the extent to which biofeedback aligns with your

present practices. How closely or distantly does biofeedback correspond to your current activities? Does anyone exhibit this behavior in this context, or does it go completely unnoticed?

Part 2 questions:

In this section, we calculated the median score for these recommendations, which was interesting. In this section of our discussion, we will concentrate on recommendations that garnered a robust consensus for their inclusion in the management of gait disorders following stroke. We wondered why you think there might have been such high consensus, and why perhaps a handful of people fully agreed to include these kinds of recommendations in their practice in gait disorders rehabilitation after stroke? What caused the participants to show little variance in their practice of including or excluding these types of suggestions for gait abnormalities after stroke?

Part 3 questions

In this section, our focus will be on recommendations that have received ratings falling within a range of consensus to rejection. This indicates that the recommendations haven't reached a sufficient level of consensus or rejection.